

A Brief Introduction to Non-Cooperation Movement: Its Features, Causes and Limitations

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Abstract

The Non-Cooperation Movement, initiated by Mahatma Gandhi in 1920, aimed to be a nonviolent protest against British rule in India. This movement encouraged Indians to resign from their government titles and honors, thereby rejecting the colonial administration's recognition. Additionally, it called for a boycott of government educational institutions, courts, and services to undermine the British authority and weaken its functioning. Indians were urged to shun foreign goods and promote the use of domestic products, fostering economic self-reliance. The movement also involved boycotting elections to delegitimize the British-controlled political system. Ultimately, it aspired to culminate in the refusal to pay taxes, further challenging the financial foundation of British governance in India. Through these collective actions, the Non-Cooperation Movement sought to assert Indian autonomy and pave the way for independence.

1. Introduction

India's struggle for independence began when Indians refused to get overpowered by the Britishers and planned to work together towards an independent India. But, the process wasn't easy. There were hurdles all through the way. Many movements were launched with an effort to throw British powers outside India, but most of them failed in fulfilling the purpose they were started for. But, they strengthened India's will towards freedom and finally paved the path towards an independent India.

The non-cooperation movement, popularly known as the civil disobedience movement, was launched on 1 August 1920 by Mahatma Gandhi. The non-cooperation movement was the first mass movement organized as a part of India's freedom struggle. It aimed to resist British authority through nonviolent means, including boycotting British goods, institutions, and titles, and promoting Indian self-reliance. This movement marked a shift towards mass involvement in the Indian independence struggle and highlighted the power of nonviolent resistance as a political tool. However, it was suspended in 1922 after the Chauri Chaura incident, where violence erupted, leading Gandhi to call off the movement to maintain its nonviolent character.

Non-cooperation with evil is as much a duty as is cooperation with good.

By- M.K.Gandhi

2. Background of the movement

The Non-Cooperation Movement was a significant protest in India's struggle for independence against British rule. It was launched by Mahatma Gandhi on 1 August 1920. The movement aimed to resist British rule through peaceful means, urging Indians to boycott British goods, institutions, and government functions. The trigger for this movement was the Jallianwala Bagh massacre in 1919 and the British government's repressive Rowlatt Act. Despite its suspension in 1922 after incidents of violence in Chauri Chaura, the Non-Cooperation Movement marked a turning point in India's fight for freedom, fostering mass mobilization and nationalist sentiment.

Many reasons triggered the non-cooperation movement of which the most important ones were:

A. The Jallianwala Bagh massacre

The Jallianwala Bagh massacre is an event that will never be forgotten. On April 13, 1919, a large crowd gathered to peacefully protest against the arrest of Dr Satyapal and Dr Saifuddin Kitchlew. This crowd of unarmed innocent women, children, and men were open fire with machine guns and rifles on the orders of General Dyer. Thousands of people were killed during this Massacre. After this, martial law was imposed in Punjab, and the people had to face hardships that they never imagined.

B. Unhappy with the reforms introduced in Montagu – Chelmsford

The government of India act 1919 was enacted based on the recommendations of the Montagu-Chelmsford proposals made in 1918. The right to vote was curtailed, and the Indians had little or no say in the decisions and policies framed by the government. However, Indians refused to give in and decided to protest against the government of India act and its recommendations. This list introduced the Dyarchy system and divided the topics in the list into reserved and transferred.

C. Rowlatt act

The Rowlatt act of 1919 entitles the police with supreme rights to imprison anyone suspected of terrorism for a minimum of 2 years without trial. Gandhi organized a mass protest against this movement across different parts of the country.

D. Khilafat movement

The Khilafat movement, which began in 1919, brought the Hindus and the Muslims United under one roof. They decided to stand against the injustices done by the Britishers, and that was the beginning of the non-cooperation movement.

E. Economic Exploitation

Indians faced economic exploitation under British rule, with high taxes and unfair trade policies. These economic grievances created a sense of discontent and resentment among the Indian population.

F. Desire for Swaraj

The Non-Cooperation Movement was driven by the Indian people's strong desire for Swaraj. They were inspired by the principles of non-violence and civil disobedience advocated by Mahatma Gandhi. Gandhi believed that non-cooperation with British authorities would eventually lead to independence.

3. Salient Features of the Non-cooperation Movement

- i. The movement was mostly a nonviolent and peaceful protest against British rule in India.
- ii. As a protest, Indians were urged to forfeit their titles and resign from appointed seats in local bodies.
- iii. Employees were requested to resign from their positions with the British government.
- iv. Parents were asked to pull their children out of government-run or assisted schools and colleges.
- v. People were encouraged to boycott imported goods in favour of those created in India.
- vi. Voters were asked to boycott the legislative council elections.
- vii. No one was allowed to join the British army.
- viii. If the aforementioned steps failed to produce results, it was also envisaged that people would refuse to pay their taxes.
- ix. Swarajya, or self-government, was also a demand of the INC.
- x. The non-cooperation campaign was a watershed moment in the independence movement because, for the first time, the INC was willing to sacrifice constitutional measures in order to obtain self-rule.
- xi. If the campaign was carried out to its conclusion, Gandhiji promised that Swaraj would be attained in a year.

4. Role of Mahatma Gandhiji in Non-Co-operation

- i. Mahatma Gandhi was a key figure in spreading the Non-Cooperation Movement's policies and initiatives across the country.
- ii. He and other loyalists went on a nationwide tour to rally public support and mobilise the masses in support of the campaign.
- iii. Several pupils quit their schools when Gandhi persuaded them to leave state institutions and join national schools.
- iv. Without question, the Non-Cooperation Cause and Gandhi's role in it catapulted the Indian independence movement to unprecedented heights. It instilled in the people a new political zeal and taught the Indians to be fearless.
- v. Swarajya found popular expression under Mahatma Gandhi's leadership, and a patriotic zeal captivated the entire nation.

- vi. Gandhi's gift to the nation, satyagraha, or passive resistance, turned out to be the Indians' greatest asset.
- vii. The promotion of khadi was a fundamental programme of The Non-Cooperation Movement.
- viii. Charkha and Indian handloom products regained their glory under Gandhi's leadership. A large number of weavers were employed.
- ix. Gandhi's contribution to this campaign, and subsequently to Indian nationalism, was that he united the entire country under a common ethos for the first time.
- x. Under his exceptional leadership, the liberation struggle took on a pan-India character.

5. Spread of Non-Cooperation Movement

The call for non-cooperation and boycott provoked massive responses from various parts of India, which were marked by massive popular protests against the British Raj. However, in most places, the movement was shaped by local conditions.

- i. Bengal: Birendranath Sasmal organised the anti-union board agitation in the Contai and Tamluk sub-divisions of Midnapore.
 - ii. Assam: J.M. Sengupta organised strikes in tea plantations, steamer services, and ii. Assam-Bengal Railways.
 - iii. United Province: Under Baba Ram Chandra's leadership, agrarian riots erupted in Rae Bareli, Pratapgarh, Fyzabad, and Sultanpur. A peasant outburst of the 'Eka movement' arose under the leadership of Madari Pasi. In Awadh, the Kisan Sabha movement was prominent.
 - iv. Punjab: The Akali movement for Gurudwara reform and control became closely associated with non-cooperation. It demonstrated remarkable communal unity among Sikhs, Muslims, and Hindus.
 - v. Rajasthan: The peasants protested against cesses and begar. The Bijolia Movement in Mewar and the Bhil Movement under Motilal Tejawat were significant movements against the exploitation by the British and Jagirs.
 - vi. Gujarat: Vallabh Patel spread the movement and regarded non-cooperation as a feasible alternative to revolutionary terrorism to fight against a colonial government.
 - vii. Karnataka: Karnataka areas were largely unaffected by the movement, and the initial reaction of upper and middle-class professional groups in several areas of the Madras presidency was limited.
- Workers at the Buckingham and Carnatic textile mills went on strike. Local Non-Cooperation leaders offered them moral support.
- viii. Andhra: In Andhra, tribal and other peasant grievances against forest laws were linked to the Non-Cooperation Movement. The peasants refused to pay taxes to the zamindars, and the entire population of Chirala-Perala refused to pay taxes and vacated the town. Alluri Sitaram

Raju organised the tribals and combined their demands with those of the Non-Cooperation Movement.

ix. Tamil Nadu: Led by C. Rajagopalachari, S. Satyamurthy and Periyar E.V.R.

Kerala: Peasants organised anti-Jemni struggles. The Mopillah revolt was very intense during this period.

6. Limitations of Non-Cooperation Movement

The Non-Cooperation Movement was a significant step in India's struggle for independence. However, it had several limitations and challenges that impacted its effectiveness.

i. Merger of Khilafat issue: The cause of the Khilafat movement was exclusively on the religious line, and then the convergence of NCM and Khilafat proved to be less useful for secular politics in India in the long term.

ii. Limited reach: While the Non-Cooperation Movement garnered substantial support, especially in urban areas, it did not have universal backing across India. The rural population had limited awareness of these movements and often remained detached.

iii. Lack of clear goal: The movements didn't have a well-defined roadmap beyond non-cooperation with the British for achieving independence or addressing broader socio-economic issues.

iv. Differences: There were differences in strategies, ideologies, and priorities that led to fragmentation and weakened the overall effectiveness of the movements. For example, there were differences regarding the boycott of legislative councils. Some leaders, such as C.R. Das, were unwilling to include a council boycott.

7. Suspension of Non-Cooperation

In the aftermath of the Chauri Chaura event, Gandhiji issued a directive to halt the movement in February 1922. In Chauri Chaura, Uttar Pradesh, a violent mob ignited a police station, resulting in the death of 22 officers amid a clash with movement protesters. Gandhiji justified calling off the movement, asserting that the populace was not prepared for an ahimsa-based insurrection against the government. However, several leaders, including Motilal Nehru and C R Das, opposed the suspension, citing sporadic acts of violence.

8. Some Important Events

i. The Treaty of Sevres with Turkey was signed in May 1920 which completely dismembered Turkey.

ii. In June 1920, an all-party conference at Allahabad approved a program of a boycott of schools, colleges, and law courts, and asked Mahatma Gandhi to lead it.

iii. On August 31, 1920, the Khilafat Committee started a campaign of non-cooperation, and the movement was formally launched.

iv. In September 1920, at a special session in Calcutta, Congress approved a non-cooperation program till the Punjab and Khilafat wrongs were removed and swaraj was established.

v. In December 1920, at the Nagpur session of the Indian National Congress; the program of non-cooperation was endorsed.

vi. Some important organizational changes were made: a Congress Working Committee (CWC) of 15 members was set up to lead the Congress from now onwards.

9. Consequences of non-cooperation movement

i. The National Congress has demonstrated that it represents the majority of the country's views. It can no longer be accused of representing a "microscopic minority."

ii. The movement was likewise widespread across the country. While some locations were more active than others, few, if any, places were completely deafeningly silent in response to the call for non-cooperation.

iii. The Non-Cooperation Movement was the people's first chance to get involved in politics and fight injustice and economic misery brought on by years of foreign domination.

iv. Despite the Malabar events, which were not repeated during the Civil Disobedience Campaign, Muslims played an important role in the movement and in maintaining communal unity.

v. Purn Swaraj was the goal of the Non-Cooperation Movement. However, it was not achieved.

vi. Because of the Cauri-Chaura incident, in which people attacked police officers, Gandhi Ji decided to cancel it.

vii. However, it was a widespread movement that caused Indians to lose faith in the British. This movement enthralled Indians.

10. Slogans of the movement.

1. Swaraj Bharat ,Swantra Bharat !!

2. Ghandi nhi ye Aandhi hai!

3. Ab nhi jalne denge aur Bagh. Jal rahi hai dil mai aajadi ki aag !

4. Apna Desh aur ho Apni Sarkaar.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we may say, while the Non-Cooperation Movement did not achieve its immediate goal of securing independence, it was instrumental in shaping the course of India's independence struggle, influencing future movements and strategies, and demonstrating the power of non-violent resistance on a national scale.

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